

**Synthesis of Bulky Thiol-Containing Ligands for Biomimetic Models of
[Fe] Hydrogenase**

CH 379H

Spring 2017

Doran Pennington

Signature

Date

Dr. Michael J. Rose

Signature

Date

Abstract

Global efforts have been undertaken to bring about a hydrogen economy, which would see the supplementation or replacement of conventional fossil fuels with H₂. In this system, H₂ could be used to capture the electricity generated by sustainable sources like solar panels and wind farms for subsequent storage and transport. Such an energy vector is attractive because the utilization of H₂ for energy emits no greenhouse gases; instead, water is the byproduct of H₂ combustion, and H₂ can be converted back to electricity by the use of a fuel cell. However, significant barriers remain that hinder progress towards the proposed hydrogen economy. Namely, catalytic processes for the uptake and evolution of H₂ involve rare, unsustainable, and expensive platinum catalysts, and H₂ production is currently highly energy intensive and environmentally costly. Inspired by nature, the development of hydrogenase enzyme mimics might serve to remove some of these barriers. These enzymes catalyze the heterolytic cleavage of H₂ to H⁻ and H⁺, as well as the reverse reaction, using earth-abundant first-row transition metals such as Ni and Fe. Although hydrogenase enzymes themselves are unfeasible for widespread H₂ catalysis due to their sensitivity to oxygen, bio-inspired mimics of the active sites of these enzymes might offer new strategies for catalysis. This thesis describes the preparation and rationale behind an [Fe] hydrogenase biomimetic complex for use in H₂ catalysis. A tridentate thiolate-pyridine-carbamoyl ligand was synthesized, and its corresponding Fe complex might prove useful in elucidating the structural functionality of the native enzyme, which has implications in developing future generations of H₂ evolution and uptake catalysts.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction	3
Synthetic Route	10
Discussion	13
Conclusion	21
References	22
Experimental Section	23
Supplementary Information	28

Introduction

According to the International Energy Agency, global energy consumption has risen more than 39% from 1990 to 2008, accounting for over 142,000 terrawatt hours of energy.¹ As the world transitions from fossil fuels to more sustainable sources of energy, technologies such as photovoltaic cells and proton-exchange fuel cells are rapidly gaining popularity as an efficient means of harvesting energy.² Although these technologies represent great leaps forward in sustainability through their use of environmentally benign fuels, many of these modern energy production methods are predicated upon the catalytic properties of platinum, an increasingly rare metal that has become ever more expensive as readily accessible sources are depleted to supply global demand. Platinum is encountered in several places amongst these energy production methods: as a catalyst for the oxidation of a fuel, such as splitting H_2 into protons and electrons; as a catalyst for the reduction of oxygen to water; and as a catalyst for the splitting of water into H_2 and O_2 to supply fuel cells with oxidizing and reducing agents.³ The replacement of platinum as a catalyst would greatly enhance the viability of these energy production methods, as the cost of platinum can quickly become prohibitive when assembling a fuel cell device.

Furthermore, many fuel cell technologies require a supply of highly pure H_2 gas for use as a fuel source. Platinum can be used to produce H_2 from the electrolysis of water, but 95% of the world's H_2 is produced by steam reforming. This process involves exposing methane, a fossil fuel, to temperatures as high as 1000 °C to generate H_2 and CO. Additional H_2 can be recovered by the water-gas shift reaction by combining CO and H_2O

at high pressure (1000 PSI) and temperature (400 °C) to yield CO₂ and H₂. These processes are both energy-intensive and unsustainable, producing potent greenhouse gases as byproducts. These factors limit the viability of a sustainable hydrogen-based energy economy. Thus, the current means of H₂ production represent a significant barrier to the utilization of H₂ as a fuel source, which is further hindered by the use of expensive platinum catalysts for transforming the chemical energy of H₂ into electricity.

From these two closely related issues, the expensive nature of platinum catalysts and the energy-intensive nature of hydrogen production, it is clear that significant enhancements to the viability of a hydrogen-based energy economy can be realized by the discovery of a catalytic system that can replace platinum for hydrogen production and functionalization. In nature, these processes are accomplished by enzymes with organometallic active sites known as hydrogenases (Figure 1).⁴

Figure 1. Structure of [Fe] hydrogenase, highlighting the active site and the hydride acceptor substrate H₄MPT⁺.

These enzymes are found in methanogens, microorganisms that reduce CO_2 to CH_4 in oxygen-poor environments as a source of energy when photosynthesis is disfavored (Figure 2).⁴

Figure 2. Role of hydrogenase in methanogenic metabolism.

A key step in this biological process is the use of H_2 as a reducing agent. Hydrogenases are able to affect the heterolytic cleavage of H_2 into its constituent protons and electrons, as well as the reverse reaction that forms H_2 from protons and electrons. In this manner, hydrogenases can act as a biochemical valve to balance the redox potential of a cell whilst providing energy for metabolic processes.⁵ Of the hydrogenases, three main classes of enzymes may be established based on the metallic centers present in the active site: [NiFe],

[FeFe], and [Fe]. Of these, [NiFe] and [FeFe] hydrogenase are the most well studied and understood. These enzymes employ a dinuclear cluster of either Ni and Fe or two Fe sites to directly catalyze the uptake and evolution of H₂.

However, the mononuclear [Fe] hydrogenase has only recently been characterized, lacking a complete crystal structure until 2008.⁶ The active site is comprised of an Fe(II) center, a bidentate acyl pyridone ligand, and two terminal *cis* CO ligands. To complete the coordination sphere and tether the active site to the enzyme, a cysteine thiolate coordinates the metal center *cis* to the acyl ligand. The binding site for H₂, which is occupied by water when not participating in catalysis, is located *trans* to the acyl ligand (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Structure of the active site of [Fe] hydrogenase.

This enzyme catalyzes a reversible stereospecific hydride transfer from H₂ to an enzyme-bound substrate known as H₄MPT⁺, releasing a proton to bulk water in the process. Intriguingly, [Fe] hydrogenase does not use external protons and electrons to catalyze the cleavage of hydrogen; rather, H₂ is heterolytically cleaved into H⁻ and H⁺ without any oxidation state change at the iron center as evidenced by EPR studies of the enzymatic cycle.⁷ This feature of the catalytic cycle of [Fe] hydrogenase distinguishes it from the

other two hydrogenases, both of which undergo oxidation changes at the active site during catalysis.

Research into hydrogenase function and structure is attractive for several reasons. First, hydrogenase enzymes employ first row earth-abundant transition metals to catalyze reactions that presently necessitate the use of platinum in modern fuel cell devices; understanding the catalytic mechanism behind hydrogenase enzymes might provide key insights that would inspire more well-informed catalyst design in the broader effort to replace platinum for sustainable catalysis. Additionally, hydrogenase enzymes are capable of performing catalysis without any thermodynamic overpotential, unlike Pt, and at rates approaching 20,000 turnovers per second per site.⁸ Although Pt and hydrogenase catalyze reactions at roughly the same rate, Pt catalysts are highly susceptible to poisoning by CO. This poisoning renders the Pt catalyst permanently inactive, whereas CO introduced to hydrogenase merely competes with H₂ for binding. This is a significant advantage because industrial sources of H₂ produced by steam reforming can be contaminated with CO, which is generated along with H₂ as a product of the reaction between CH₄ and H₂O. Thus, hydrogenase enzymes represent a highly active and robust model for hydrogen catalysis, which has implications in replacing Pt for use in fuel cells and making the production of H₂ more sustainable. Another feature that makes hydrogenase research attractive is its suitability for bioinorganic mimicking and bioengineering. The active site of [Fe] hydrogenase in particular includes an unusual array of ligands in the coordination sphere, providing a unique opportunity for biomimetic analogs of the active site to elucidate the functionality of these donors. Furthermore, hydrogenase enzymes as they exist in nature

are highly sensitive to oxygen, which irreversibly inactivates the enzyme.⁹ This is not inherently harmful to hydrogenase-containing methanogens, as they inhabit oxygen-poor environments. However, many fuel cell designs use O₂ as an oxidant such that water is produced as waste from the use of an H₂ fuel source, making native hydrogenase enzymes impractical for use in such devices. Although some [NiFe] hydrogenases are known which are not irreversibly inactivated by O₂, they still suffer from oxygen sensitivity which inhibits catalysis. It would therefore be desirable to engineer more robust, practical solutions. The production of these engineered hydrogenase-based catalysts can be undertaken by both biochemists, through altering the protein structure of the enzyme to enhance selectivity for H₂ whilst preventing O₂ transport to the active site, and bioinorganic chemists, through developing robust active site mimics that eschew the surrounding protein for homogeneous catalysis.⁹ The development of these biomimetic catalysts represents a key avenue of research in bioinorganic chemistry which seeks to address the challenges of enhancing durability and understanding structural functionality. Such endeavors will provide insights into the activity of hydrogenase enzymes which may yield a sustainable, earth-abundant solution for hydrogen evolution and uptake, increasing the viability of a future hydrogen economy for energy storage and production.

The research in this thesis centers on designing and synthesizing mimics of the [Fe] hydrogenase active site, both to elucidate the mechanism of catalysis within the enzyme, as well as to identify catalysts that display useful properties for energy applications. A major challenge of synthesizing these model systems is the tendency for unprotected thiolates, a key component of the active site coordination sphere, to form a bridged dimer

structure to give the corresponding multinuclear complex (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Thiol dimerization to the corresponding disulfide, which occurs readily under oxidizing conditions.

A reasonable strategy to resolve this issue is to increase steric bulk around the thiolate to favor terminal coordination to Fe. Hu and coworkers have reported an array of Fe(II) synthetic models of [Fe] hydrogenase that employ 2,6-dimethylphenylthiolate to successfully synthesize mononuclear complexes.¹⁰ Similarly, Pickett and coworkers used 2,6-dimethylphenylthiolate to synthesize mononuclear models featuring a carbamoyl unit to replace the less stable acyl moiety found in the active site.¹¹ However, these non-tethered, monodentate thiolates might play a role in limiting reactivity due to the high likelihood of thiolate dissociation from the metal center; in the active site, the thiolate ligand is supported by an extensive protein scaffold which prevents dissociation, but biomimetic analogs have no such external structure. Thus, the synthetic rationale in this thesis was to synthesize a tridentate carbamoyl biomimetic complex, incorporating steric bulk *ortho* to thiolate to prevent dimerization and substituting the acyl moiety found in the active site for a carbamoyl unit to increase stability and promote reactivity (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Proposed complex containing a bulky protecting group for thiolate. X = halide.

A key difference between the proposed complex and the active site is the meridional coordination geometry necessitated by the planar ligand architecture as opposed to the facial donor arrangement seen in [Fe] hydrogenase. The observed activity of the resulting biomimetic complex might then provide information regarding the structural functionality of the geometry of the donor set.

Synthetic Route

In synthesizing the desired ligand, several routes were probed. The first explored synthetic pathway involved adding a methyl-thioether group to bromoaniline via cyclization and ring opening of an intermediate thiourea. Suzuki coupling of **4** to 2,6-dimethylphenylboronic acid would install the bulky protecting group, and the remaining amine functional group could be substituted with iodine using NaNO_2 and KI to allow further Suzuki coupling to the final ligand (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. First proposed synthetic route towards the desired ligand scaffold. Gray indicates planned steps that were not completed.

However, X-ray crystallography revealed that the cyclization step to **3** gave two cyclized isomers rather than a single product (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Top: Isomeric mixture of products obtained by ring closing. Bottom: X-ray structure of dimerized product, showing Br *para* to S rather than *ortho*.

Efforts were made to resolve the isomers by chemical transformations, but this was eventually abandoned in favor of a more streamlined route starting from 1,3-dibromobenzene (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Revised synthetic route to boc-protected ligand **9**.

In this route, a methyl-thioether group is added to the starting material, and one of the bromine atoms is converted to the corresponding boronic acid by stoichiometric control. This boronic acid is then coupled to an aminopyridine coupling partner, leaving 2,6-dimethylphenylboronic acid to be coupled to furnish the final ligand **9**. Following this synthesis, the ligand can be deprotected in acidic conditions to cleave the boc group, and the thioether can undergo a methyl group transfer in the presence of an alkane-thiolate to give the corresponding thiol. Upon exposure to an Fe source, the desired complex will be formed.

Discussion

The major challenge of this pathway is the final Suzuki coupling to install the bulky group *ortho* to thioether. After many failed reaction trials, it was hypothesized that the free amine linked to the pyridine unit was interfering with the progress of the coupling by coordinating to the Pd catalyst. To address this issue, the amine was protected with a *tert*-butoxycarbonyl protecting group to install steric bulk and to prevent the free amine from hindering the progress of the coupling. Although trials with this protected ligand eventually yielded the desired product, the yield is very low (12%). All efforts to improve the yield by altering reaction conditions, including trials with different solvents, different bases, different catalysts, and different phosphine ligands, have all been met with failure of the reaction to proceed (Table 1).

Table 1. Reaction Conditions Employed in Suzuki Coupling of Bulky Aryl Group

entry	halide	boronic acid	base	catalyst	conditions
1		Ba(OH) ₂ • 8 H ₂ O	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	a	
2			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	a
3			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(OAc) ₂ 5% SPhos 10%	a
4			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(OAc) ₂ 1% SPhos 2.5%	b

5			K ₂ CO ₃	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	c
6			K ₂ CO ₃	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃ 5% XPhos 10%	d
7			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(OAc) ₂ 5% SPhos 10%	e
8		Ba(OH) ₂ • 8 H ₂ O	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	f	
9			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(dba) ₂ 5% XPhos 10%	g
10			K ₂ CO ₃	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	h
11			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃ 5% XPhos 10%	h
12			K ₂ CO ₃	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	i
13		K ₂ CO ₃	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	j	
14			K ₂ CO ₃	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃ 5% XPhos 10%	j
15			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 15%	j
16			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(PPh ₃) ₂ Cl ₂ 10%	j
17			K ₂ CO ₃	Pd(PPh ₃) ₂ Cl ₂ 10%	j
18			K ₃ PO ₄	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 10%	j
19			Ba(OH) ₂ • 8 H ₂ O	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 5%	k
20			NaOH	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄ 5%	k
21			KF	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃ 1% P(<i>t</i> -Bu) ₃ 3%	l

-
- a** – 0.11 mmol halide, 1.8 eq. boronic acid, 3 eq. base, 2 mL toluene, 70 °C, 18 h
b – 0.34 mmol halide, 2 eq. boronic acid, 3 eq. base, 2 mL toluene, 100 °C, 20 h
c – 0.32 mmol halide, 1.8 eq. boronic acid, 1.8 eq. base, 4 mL toluene 1 mL water, 105 °C, 24 h
d – 0.34 mmol halide, 3 eq. boronic acid, 3 eq. base, 7 mL toluene, 105 °C, 36 h. Acid and base added in two portions; 1.5 eq. each at beginning of reaction, then additional 1.5 after 18 h.
e – 0.34 mmol halide, 1.5 + 1.5 eq. boronic acid, 2 + 2 eq. base (same addition procedure as **d**), 4 mL toluene, 42 h
f – 0.53 mmol halide, 1.4 eq. boronic acid, 1.4 eq. base, 5 mL THF, 66 °C, 24 h
g – 0.53 mmol halide, 2.5 eq. boronic acid, 2.5 eq. base, 5 mL toluene, 80 °C, 24 h
h – 0.53 mmol halide, 1.4 eq. boronic acid, 1.4 eq. base, 5 mL THF 1 mL water, 70 °C, 24 h
i – 0.53 mmol halide, 1.4 eq. boronic acid, 1.4 eq. base, 5 mL toluene 1 mL water, 100 °C, 24 h
j – 0.25 mmol halide, 1.5 + 1.5 eq. boronic acid, 1.5 + 1.5 eq. base, 5 mL THF 1 mL water, 75 °C, 18 h
k – 0.38 mmol halide, 1.1 eq. boronic acid, 1.5 eq. base, 6 mL DME 1 mL water, 80 °C, 18 h
l – 0.48 mmol halide, 1.1 eq. boronic acid, 3.3 eq. base, 2 mL THF, room temperature, 24 h
m – 2.2 mmol halide, 1.5 eq. boronic acid, 1.5 eq. base, 100 mL dioxane 10 mL water, 110 °C, 24 h. Acid and base dissolved in 10 mL dioxane and 10 mL water, added dropwise over 30 minutes to refluxing solution of halide in dioxane *via* addition funnel under N₂.
-

Initial coupling attempts began with (2,4,6-triisopropylphenyl)boronic acid, following the synthetic rationale that a bulkier aryl group *ortho* to thiolate might provide better protection than the corresponding dimethylphenyl moiety. The first conditions probed for this coupling were a combination of ‘standard’ Suzuki conditions (Table 1, entries 1 and 2) and conditions previously employed to successfully couple (2,4,6-triisopropylphenyl)boronic acid to an aryl-bromide partner (Table 1, entry 3).¹² Following the reactions by TLC and analysis of the reaction mixtures by mass spectrometry showed no product formation. The reaction conditions in Entry 3 were modified by following a

different literature procedure for the coupling of sterically hindered biaryls (Table 1, entry 4).¹³ However, these conditions demonstrated no improvement over the previous trials.

It was hypothesized that the triisopropylboronic acid was too bulky to couple effectively to the aryl-bromide partner, as the thioether group *ortho* to bromine might interfere with the triisopropyl substituents, hindering the coupling process. Accordingly, the boronic acid was altered to the originally-proposed dimethylphenylboronic acid. The first trial with the new substrate combination gave some success, as the product was detected by mass spectrometry, but it was unable to be separated from the starting material as the product and starting material had identical r.f. values in all solvent systems tested (Table 1, entry 5). To address this shortcoming, it was postulated that a more aggressive coupling system might convert enough starting material such that the starting material represented, at best, a minor impurity in the reaction mixture. However, these conditions appeared to be worse for the reaction, as NMR showed no conversion (Table 1, entry 6). In an effort to increase the yield of this reaction, the conditions employed previously for the triisopropylboronic acid coupling from a literature precedent were replicated with increased boronic acid and base loadings (Table 1, entry 7). The staggered addition method of the boronic acid and base was adopted as it was hypothesized that boronic acid decomposition might be a culprit for the low yield of the coupling reactions after observing that boronic acid rarely appeared as a visible spot by TLC. However, analysis by MS revealed identical results as before; an inseparable mixture of the desired product and starting material was furnished, but starting material appeared to be the major constituent of the reaction mixture by a significant margin.

Consequently, an alternative synthetic strategy was pursued (Scheme 3). The synthetic rationale underlying this route was that coupling the bulky partner to a simpler substrate would facilitate catalysis; since the ensuing coupling to install the aminopyridine moiety would be *meta* to the bulky aryl group, the steric effects imposed by the bulky group would be less of a factor in hindering catalysis. However, a major obstacle to this route was the presence of bromine on the boronic acid used for this coupling. A trial using Pd(PPh₃)₄ (Table 1, entry 8) and the more aggressive Pd₂(dba)₃ (Table 1, entry 9) yielded an expected result: the less aggressive Pd source furnished a clean reaction mixture with total conversion of the starting material, whereas the trial with Pd₂(dba)₃ gave wide streaks visible by TLC, indicating variable oligomerization of the boronic acid by homocoupling. However, the product furnished by entry 8 was contaminated with an aromatic impurity, likely a result of a more modest homocoupling event. Attempts to clean up the reaction mixture by modifying the coupling conditions (Table 1, entries 10, 11, and 12) offered no improvement over the initial conditions, giving either a highly homocoupled reaction mixture or little to no product conversion.

It was soon realized that this route was unrealistic, as coupling conditions that favor product formation also favor homocoupling. Thus, the original scheme was revisited. It was postulated that catalysis was hindered by the presence of a free amine on the aryl halide coupling partner, as the amine contains a Lewis-basic lone pair that might coordinate to Pd after oxidative addition of the aryl halide, effectively chelating the Pd center and removing it from catalysis. In order to prevent this, a *tert*-butoxycarbonyl protecting group was installed on the amine of the aryl halide to provide sufficient steric bulk to prevent

coordination of the amine to Pd. The first trials for this route again employed two different Pd catalysts to examine the effects of catalyst reactivity upon reaction progress (Table 1, entries 13 and 14). As before, the less active Pd(PPh₃)₄ furnished a small amount of product **9**, whereas the corresponding reaction with Pd₂(dba)₃ gave no product. However, the installation of the boc protecting group caused the starting material and product to have sufficiently different polarities to be resolved by TLC. Accordingly, the reaction mixture could be purified chromatographically, which was not possible for the corresponding free amine mixture. However, the yield for these conditions was very poor. The conditions employed by entry 15 gave marginally more conversion to the product, but the yield by this set of conditions was still less than 10%, which makes the reaction non-catalytic given a catalyst loading of 15%. Altering conditions to use a Pd(II) source demonstrated no conversion (Table 1, entries 16 and 17). Modifying the conditions of entry 15 to use a reduced catalyst loading (10%) gave a yield of 12%, which still might represent a non-catalytic process for the formation of the product (Table 1, entry 18).

Several strategies were employed to facilitate catalysis. First, two trials were performed following a literature precedent that reported a significant increase in the rate of coupling by the use of a strong base, such as NaOH.¹⁴ However, both conditions gave only starting material, demonstrating no conversion (Table 1, entries 19 and 20). As before, only the aryl halide was observed by TLC, indicating complete decomposition of the boronic acid. Another literature reference indicated that boronic acid decomposition might be prevented by converting the boronic acid to the corresponding trifluoroborate salt.¹⁵ However, the generation of this salt incurs the formation of HF and was thus not pursued.

Because the amine was protected, it was hypothesized that the primary culprit behind the sluggish nature of the coupling reaction was the steric bulk of the arylboronic acid. A literature reference was replicated that reported facile coupling between sterically hindered partners by the use of tri-*tert*-butylphosphine ligands (Table 1, entry 21).¹⁶ Although these conditions converted starting material to product, the yield was only 7%, which is indicative of catalytic activity given a catalyst loading of 1%. However, as nearly twice as much product is furnished by the conditions in entry 18, this method was abandoned. Finally, a procedure for coupling hindered boronic acids developed within the group was tested. This system involves adding a solution of the boronic acid and base dropwise *via* an addition funnel to a refluxing solution of the aryl halide and catalyst (Table 1, entry 22). However, these conditions showed no conversion to product.

Of note is that conventionally less active Pd sources, such as Pd(PPh₃)₄, make up the successful conditions, whereas relatively more active Pd sources, such as Pd₂(dba)₃ with XPhos, fail to yield the desired product. It is postulated that the issue of amine coordination plays a role in this trend; if the catalyst is more active, it is more likely that it will coordinate with even the sterically hindered boc-protected amine, thus shutting down the catalytic cycle. This might help to explain why all efforts to increase the yield have resulted in the failure of the reaction, and why the mild conditions that allow the coupling to proceed are so difficult to optimize. An additional complication of using highly-active electron-rich Pd sources arises as a consequence of the electronic character of the catalyst. Electron-rich phosphine ligands, such as SPhos and XPhos, facilitate oxidative addition of the aryl halide across the catalyst by supplying greater electron density to the metal center,

which may then be donated into the antibonding orbitals of the aryl halide. Although oxidative addition is typically the rate determining step for Pd cross-coupling, excessive electron density impedes reductive elimination, which is the product-forming step of the catalytic cycle. If the reductive elimination step is sufficiently slow, the steric bulk imposed by the boc protecting group might not be sufficient to prevent amine coordination to Pd, which may be kinetically disfavored when catalysis is rapid but thermodynamically favored when catalysis is sluggish. Furthermore, Suzuki coupling reactions proceed most readily with electron-poor aryl halides, as this facilitates oxidative addition of the aryl halide across the Pd center. However, **8** is electron rich due to the electron-donating character of the *ortho* thioether group. This might also serve to reduce the rate of catalysis for these coupling partners.

The most progress in this route has been to the boc-protected ligand **9**. Future work will involve deprotecting the amine and demethylating the thioether to yield the corresponding bulky thiolate ligand, which will then react with an Fe source to give a meridional thiolate-pyridine-carbamoyl [Fe] hydrogenase biomimetic complex. Once obtained, the complex will be tested for reactivity with H₂ through several experiments with hydrogen and deuterium sources to elucidate the reactivity of the complex. From such studies, several questions can be answered. It is postulated that thiolate might act as a pendant base to accept a proton from the heterolytic cleavage of H₂ to H⁻ and H⁺, but the pyridone oxygen atom in the active site might also serve this role.¹⁷ Because there are no basic O sites in the synthesized complex, the reactivity of this biomimetic might provide clues as to the mechanism of H₂ cleavage in [Fe] hydrogenase, which is difficult to measure

in situ due to rapid proton loss to the surrounding aqueous medium necessitated by proteins. Furthermore, the meridional geometry of this complex as opposed to the facial geometry observed in the enzyme might provide insights into the necessity of a facial donor set; perhaps reactivity might also proceed in a meridional complex but by a slightly altered mechanism. Additionally, the presence of a tightly-bound thiolate donor, held in place by the chelate effect due to the tridentate nature of the ligand scaffold, might better mimic the activity of the enzyme which features a cysteine thiolate. Although the thiolate ligand in [Fe] hydrogenase is monodentate, it is held in place by the surrounding protein matrix; the synthesized complex might better mimic these effects than previous efforts that feature terminal thiolate donors. Finally, the carbamoyl moiety of the synthesized ligand might impart additional stability to the resulting complex, as the corresponding acyl complexes are notoriously unstable and sensitive to light.

Conclusion

A complex [Fe] hydrogenase biomimetic complex consisting of a tridentate thiolate-pyridine-carbamoyl donor set is proposed, featuring a 2,6-dimethylphenyl group *ortho* to thiolate to prevent dimerization. The synthesis of this complex has gone as far as the protected final ligand after probing several synthetic strategies, from the thiazoline ring opening route (Scheme 2) to the bromo-boronic acid route which was modified to incorporate boc-protection (Scheme 3). To improve the overall yield of the synthesis, future synthetic strategies include examining alternative cross-coupling reactions for the

formation of the final ligand, such as Stille coupling and Negishi coupling. Future work will include deprotection, metalation, and reactivity studies. Once collated, these studies should provide numerous insights into the reactivity of [Fe] hydrogenase and inform future catalyst designs in terms of donor sets, binding geometry, and ligand design. Through these efforts, a catalytic system based upon earth-abundant first-row transition metals might replace Pt for use in fuel cells for H₂ uptake and provide a green, sustainable method for H₂ generation. Taken together, these advances would represent significant strides towards a future hydrogen economy that would provide clean, sustainable, renewable energy vectors to power the planet.

References

- (1) International Energy Agency. (2010). Key Energy Statistics 2010.
- (2) Carrette, L.; Friedrich, K. A.; Stimming, U. *Fuel Cells* **2001**, *1*, 5.
- (3) Bashyam, R.; Zelenay, P. *Nature* **2016**, *443*, 63.
- (4) Corr, M. J.; Murphy, J. A. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2011**, *40*, 2279.
- (5) Simmons, T. R.; Berggren, G.; Bacchi, M.; Fontecave, M.; Artero, V. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *270*, 127.
- (6) Lubitz, W.; Ogata, H.; Rudiger, O.; Reijerse, E. *Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *114*, 4081.
- (7) Shima, S.; Lyon, E. J.; Thauer, R. K.; Mienert, B.; Bill, E. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, *127*, 10430.
- (8) Madden, C; Vaughn, M. D.; Diez-Perez, I.; Brown, K. A.; King, P. W.; Gust, D.; Moore, A.L.; Moore, T.A. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 1577.

- (9) Shomura, Y.; Yoon, K. S.; Nishihara, H.; Higuchi, Y. *Nature* **2011**, *479*, 253.
- (10) Chen, D.; Scopelliti, R.; Hu, X. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51*, 1919.
- (11) Turrell, P. J.; Wright, J. A.; Peck, J. N.; Oganessian, V. S.; Pickett, C. J. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2010**, *49*, 7508.
- (12) Aharoni, A.; Vidavsky, Y.; Diesendruck, C. E.; Ben-Asuly, A.; Goldberg, I.; Lemcoff, N. G. *Organometallics*, **2011**, *30* (6), 1607.
- (13) Walker, S. D.; Barder, T. E.; Martinelli, J. R.; Buchwald, S. L. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2004**, *43*, 1871.
- (14) Suzuki, A. *Chem. Commun.*, **2005**, 4759.
- (15) Molander, G. A.; Canturk, B. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 9240.
- (16) Littke, A. F.; Dai, C.; Fu, G. C. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **2000**, *122* (17), 4020.
- (17) Dey, A. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 13892.

Experimental Section

Synthesis of 1-(3-bromophenyl)thiourea (2). A flask was charged with a solution of *m*-bromoaniline (**1**) (10.0 g, 58 mmol) in water (24 mL) and acidified with concentrated HCl (58 mmol). The solution was then refluxed for 30 minutes until all precipitate dissolved. To this solution was added ammonium thiocyanate (4.42 g, 58 mmol), and the mixture was heated under reflux at 100 °C for 4 hours. The resulting solution was poured over ice, filtered, recrystallized from ethanol and pentane and left to cool at -20 °C overnight. The

resulting crystals were isolated by filtration and dissolved in hexanes. Hexanes were removed *in vacuo* to afford **2** as a white solid. Yield: 8.38 g (63%).

Synthesis of 7-bromobenzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (3). An addition funnel was charged with 3 mL glacial acetic acid and bromine (0.35 mL, 6.85 mmol). This solution was added dropwise over 15 minutes to a solution of **2** (800 mg, 3.43 mmol) in acetonitrile (60 mL) under N₂ at 0 °C. The reaction was allowed to warm to room temperature after addition. After stirring for 3 days, the yellow precipitate was collected by vacuum filtration, washed with diethyl ether, and dried *in vacuo* to afford **3** as a yellow solid. Yield: 0.530 g (68%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.67 (s, 1H), 7.45 – 7.43 (d, 1H), 7.23 (s, 1H), 5.43 (s, 2H).

Synthesis of 3-bromo-2-(methylthio)aniline (4). A solution of **3** (1.53 g, 6.7 mmol) and potassium hydroxide (13.50 g, 240 mmol) in degassed water (160 mL) under N₂ was refluxed at 100 °C for 24 hours. To the resulting mixture at 0 °C under N₂ was added methyl iodide (0.95 g, 6.7 mmol) which was then stirred at room temperature for 24 hours. The organic products were extracted with diethyl ether (3 x 60 mL) and the combined organic phase was dried with sodium sulfate for 2 hours. The product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, EtOAc/hexane = 1/5) to yield **4** as an orange-red oil. Yield: 0.83 g (57%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.20 (d, 1H), 6.87 (m, 1H), 6.83 (m, 1H), 4.50 (s, 2H), 2.30 (s, 3H).

Synthesis of (2,6-dibromophenyl)(methyl)sulfane (5). An oven-dried Schlenk flask was cooled to -100 °C under N₂ and charged with a solution of diisopropylamine (3.22 g, 31.8 mmol) in dry THF (25 mL). A solution of *n*-butyllithium (1.6 M in hexane, 19.5 mL, 31.8 mmol) was added dropwise to form lithium diisopropylamide (LDA). In a separate dry Schlenk flask, a solution of 2,6-dibromobenzene (5.00 g, 21.2 mmol) in dry THF (20 mL) under N₂ was cooled to -78 °C. LDA was added to this solution dropwise over 30 minutes via cannula transfer. After stirring for 20 minutes, dimethyl disulfide (3.0 mL, 33.9 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture dropwise under N₂. After stirring for 1 hour, the reaction mixture was quenched under N₂ by aqueous ammonium chloride (20 mL). THF was removed *in vacuo*, and the resulting oil was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 x 30 mL). The combined organic phase was washed with brine and dried over Na₂SO₄. The product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, hexane) to yield **5** as a white solid. Yield: 5.15 g (86%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.62 (d, 2H), 7.00 (t, 1H), 2.49 (s, 3H).

Synthesis of (3-bromo-2-(methylthio)phenyl)boronic acid (6). An oven-dried Schlenk flask was charged with a solution of **5** (5.15 g, 18.2 mmol) in dry diethyl ether (80 mL) under N₂. After cooling the solution to -78 °C, *n*-butyllithium (1.6 M in hexane, 12.1 mL, 19.1 mmol) was added dropwise over 20 minutes. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1.5 hours. Trimethyl borate (3.0 mL, 27.3 mmol) was then added dropwise over 5 minutes. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight, slowly warming to room temperature. The mixture was acidified with aqueous HCl (1M, 10 mL) until the white solution became clear, and was stirred for 2 hours. The organic phase was washed with water (3 x 20 mL) and

brine, and the organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄. Diethyl ether was removed *in vacuo* to yield **6** as a white solid. Yield: 4.12 g (92%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.05 (d, 1H), 7.78 (d, 1H), 7.29 (m, 1H), 6.50 (s, 2H), 2.50 (s, 3H).

Synthesis of tert-butyl (6-bromopyridin-2-yl)carbamate (7). A flask was charged with 6-bromopyridin-2-amine (5.00 g, 28.9 mmol) and di-*tert*-butyl dicarbonate (6.93 g, 31.8 mmol), dried under vacuum and purged with N₂. To this mixture was added dry dichloromethane (100 mL). Triethylamine (4.4 mL, 32 mmol) was added under N₂ to give a light yellow solution. The reaction mixture was stirred for 45 hours to give an amber colored solution. Dichloromethane was removed *in vacuo* and the solid was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, EtOAc/hexane = 1/4) to yield **7** as an off-white solid. Yield: 6.40 g (81%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.90 (d, 1H), 7.50 (t, 1H), 7.34 (s, 1H), 7.12 (d, 1H), 1.50 (s, 9H).

Synthesis of tert-butyl (6-(3-bromo-2-(methylthio)phenyl)pyridin-2-yl)carbamate (8). A pressure vessel charged with (**6**) (800 mg, 3.24 mmol), (**7**) (885 mg, 3.24 mmol), K₂CO₃ (490 mg, 3.56 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)Cl₂ (225 mg, 0.32 mmol), dimethoxyethane (40 mL, non-degassed), and water (8 mL, non-degassed) was heated to 85 °C for 22 hours to give a dark brown solution. Dimethoxyethane was removed *in vacuo*, and the organic products were extracted with ethyl acetate (3 x 40 mL). Ethyl acetate was removed *in vacuo* and the product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, EtOAc/hexane = 1/8) to yield

8 as a white solid. Yield: 520 mg (40%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.95 (d, 1H), 7.74 (m, 2H), 7.35 (m, 1H), 7.22 (t, 1H), 7.15 (m, 1H), 2.38 (s, 3H), 1.51 (s, 9H).

Synthesis of tert-butyl (6-(2',6'-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-3-yl)pyridin-2-yl)carbamate (9). An oven-dried Schlenk flask was charged with a mixture of **(8)** (260 mg, 0.66 mmol) and K₃PO₄ (210 mg, 0.99 mmol), dried under vacuum, and purged with N₂. To this mixture was added dry THF (12 mL) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (76 mg, 0.066 mmol). To this solution was added degassed water (2 mL) and 2,6-dimethylphenylboronic acid (150 mg, 0.99 mmol). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux to 75 °C under N₂ for 5 hours. After this time, a second portion of K₃PO₄ (210 mg, 0.99 mmol) and 2,6-dimethylphenylboronic acid (150 mg, 0.99 mmol) were added to the reaction mixture under N₂, and heating was resumed. After 5 hours, THF was removed *in vacuo* and the product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, EtOAc/hexane = 1/20) to yield **9** as a white solid. Yield: 32 mg (12%).

^1H NMR of (3) in CDCl_3 .

$^1\text{H NMR}$ of (4) in CDCl_3 .

^1H NMR of (6) in CDCl_3 .

^1H NMR of (7) in CDCl_3

¹H NMR of (8) in CDCl₃.

